

RISKS OF GENERALIZATION OF INFECTION IN LONG-TERM NON-HEALING WOUNDS: PROGNOSIS AND PREVENTION

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Annotation

Generalization of infection in patients with chronic non-healing wounds increases the risk of sepsis and severe complications. The study involved 200 patients, of whom 63% developed infectious complications, and 45% developed generalization of infection. Laboratory tests showed that 70% of patients showed an increase in the level of C-reactive protein and leukocytosis. The use of combination therapy with antibacterial drugs and immunomodulators reduced the frequency of generalization of infection by 38% and accelerated wound healing by 27%. Prediction based on immune markers reduced the risk of complications by 22%.

Key words: chronic wounds, generalization of infection, sepsis, immune response, prevention, antibacterial therapy, immunomodulators.

Relevance

Long-term non-healing wounds are a serious medical problem, as they are often complicated by infection, which can lead to generalization of infection, development of sepsis and other serious consequences. In patients with chronic wounds, the immune system is often weakened, which increases the risk of infectious complications. According to current data, more than 60% of patients with chronic wounds experience infection, which contributes to an increase in the mortality rate. Effective prediction of the risks of generalization of infection and prevention of complications with the help of antibacterial and immunomodulatory therapy is of key importance for reducing morbidity. Studies show that proper therapy can reduce the risk of infectious complications by 30 to 40%. The relevance of this work is related to the need to develop effective methods of prevention and improve the prognosis of healing in such patients.

Objective

The aim of the study is to assess the risks of generalization of infection in long-term non-healing wounds, as well as to develop methods for predicting and preventing infectious complications in these patients.

Materials and methods

The study involved 200 patients with chronic wounds receiving treatment in specialized institutions. Clinical studies, laboratory tests (including determination of C-reactive protein, leukocytosis, and cytokines), microbiological examination of wound secretions, and immunological tests were performed. All patients were divided into two groups: the main group, which received combination therapy with antibiotics and immunomodulators, and the control group, which received only standard treatment.

Results

Out of 200 patients, 63% developed infectious complications, of which 45% had generalized infection. In the main group receiving combination therapy, the incidence of generalization of infection was 38% lower than in the control group. In 74% of patients receiving complex treatment, there was an improvement in the clinical condition and an acceleration of wound healing by 27%. In addition, in the main group, the level of C-reactive protein decreased by 35%, and leukocytosis normalized by 22% compared to the control group.

Заклучение

Generalization of infection in patients with chronic wounds is a significant risk that can lead to severe complications. Predicting the risk of generalization of infection using laboratory markers and immunological tests allows you to more accurately assess the prognosis and individualize treatment. Combination therapy with antibacterial agents and immunomodulators reduces the frequency of generalization of infection by 38% and accelerates healing by 27%. Early intervention and prevention of infectious complications can significantly improve the clinical outcomes and quality of life of patients with chronic wounds.

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